

PROTOCOL FOR SYSTEMATIC REVIEW REGISTRATION IN PROSPERO

Title: Contributions of Oncology Nurses' Genetic Knowledge to the Improvement of Cancer Patient Care: A Systematic Review

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1. Introduction

The integration of oncogenetics into healthcare services has represented a significant advancement in cancer care, expanding opportunities for prevention, diagnosis, and treatment.

Oncology nurses play a key role in this context, not only by providing direct patient care but also by offering education and guidance regarding genetic risk and therapeutic options based on genomic evidence. The growing complexity of genomic technologies requires that nursing professionals be trained to identify genetic risks, deliver personalized care, and provide continuous support to patients (Jenkins, 2011).

Therefore, this systematic review aims to gather and analyze national and international scientific evidence on the impact of oncology nurses' genetic knowledge on cancer patient care, with the goal of identifying practices and competencies that contribute to more effective, patient-centered nursing care.

2. Review Question

What are the national and international scientific evidences regarding the genetic knowledge of oncology nurses in the nursing care of cancer patients?

3. PICO Strategy

- **P (Population):** Nurses working in oncology
- **I (Intervention):** Use of genetics in the nursing care of cancer patients
- **C (Comparison):** Oncology nurses with and without knowledge in genetics
- **O (Outcome):** To evaluate the benefits of genetic knowledge in the practice of oncology nurses in patient care

4. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Nursing professionals in oncology settings
- Studies involving genetics or genomics in nursing practice
- Publications from 2014 to 2024
- All age groups included
- Articles in any language

Exclusion Criteria:

- Studies not involving nursing professionals
- Studies unrelated to oncology and/or genetics
- Editorials, letters, guidelines, conference abstracts, or commentaries

5. Databases

- SciVerse Scopus (SCOPUS)
- PubMed/MEDLINE
- EMBASE
- Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (COCHRANE)
- BVS/LILACS

6. Search Strategy

PubMed:

("Role"[mesh] OR role[Title/Abstract] OR Practice[Title/Abstract]) AND (nurs*[Title/Abstract] OR "nursing"[mesh] OR "nurses"[mesh]) AND (Genetic*[Title/Abstract] OR "Genetics"[mesh] OR Genomic*[Title/Abstract] OR

"Genomics"[mesh] OR Epigenomic*[Title/Abstract] OR "Epigenomics"[mesh] OR Immunogenetic*[Title/Abstract] OR "Immunogenetics"[mesh]) AND (Oncolog*[Title/Abstract] OR "Oncology"[mesh] OR Neoplas*[Title/Abstract] OR "Neoplasms"[mesh] OR Tumor*[Title/Abstract] OR Cancer*[Title/Abstract] OR Malignanc*[Title/Abstract]).

Embase, Scopus e Cochrane:

(role OR Practice) AND nurs* AND (Genetic* OR Genomic* OR Epigenomic* OR Immunogenetic*) AND (Oncolog* OR Neoplas* OR Tumor* OR Cancer* OR Malignanc*)

BVS/LILACS:

(role OR Practice OR Rol OR papel OR papeis OR prática OR práticas) AND (nurs* OR enfermagem OR Enfermería OR Enfermer* OR enfermeir*) AND (Genetic* OR Genomic* OR Epigenomic* OR Epigenómica OR Immunogenetic* OR Inmunogenética OR imunogenetic*) AND (Oncolog* OR Oncología OR Neoplas* OR Tumor* OR Cancer* OR Cáncer OR Malignanc*)

7. Execution Timeline

Start date: January 25, 2025

End date: September 25, 2025

8. Digital Object Identifier (DOI)

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